

The Efficacy of ChatGPT Model GPT-3.5 in Rewriting Bias out of Text while Retaining User Engagement

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Abstract

This study evaluates the capability of ChatGPT as evaluator of media bias while also examining to serve as an automated debiasing assistant for news content. We propose a three-phase pipeline - Identify, Rewrite, Evaluate - applied to a stratified dataset drawn from news outlets across the political spectrum, selected using Ad Fontes Media bias ratings, using a novel scoring framework to quantify bias across three dimensions: Framing, Emotional language, and Divisive language (F.E.D. scores). Following an explicit validation of the bias evaluation framework against established bias ratings and inter-model consistency, automated analysis of high-bias sentences (F.E.D. ≥ 6) shows significant reductions in perceived bias: 79%, 69%, and 78% across the three dimensions, respectively. Human evaluation confirms that rewrites are perceived as less biased (original texts selected as more biased 356 times vs. 90 for rewrites). However, a key trade-off emerges: participants preferred the original, more biased content for engagement (90 selections) over ChatGPT rewrites (48). This indicates that naive debiasing capabilities may inadvertently strip away engaging journalistic elements. We conclude that while large language models are effective for bias detection and suggestion, their optimal role is assistive, flagging content for human editors rather than operating autonomously. Future work must address the core challenge of reducing bias without incurring a significant engagement penalty.

1. Introduction

The proliferation of biased news content presents a significant challenge to informed public discourse and democratic decision-making. Media bias, which often manifests through emotional language, selective framing, and divisive rhetoric, can shape public perception and exacerbate societal polarization. Concurrently, large language models (LLMs) like

ChatGPT have demonstrated remarkable proficiency in text generation and analysis, prompting exploration of their use in journalistic tasks, including the potential to identify and mitigate bias.

As LLM integration in newsrooms moves from speculation to practice, a rigorous evaluation of these tools' capabilities and limitations becomes urgent. An LLM that could assist editors or readers by flagging and neutrally rewriting biased passages—provided its evaluations can be independently validated—would offer a scalable aid for upholding journalistic standards.

2. Literature Review

Early approaches to debiasing relied on rule-based systems and supervised learning, and early metrics like ROUGE and BLEU captured surface-level similarity but failed to assess bias reduction or factual consistency. Pryzant, et al. (2020) offered the first parallel corpus of biased language from 180K Wikipedia edits to determine word impact on sentence-level semantics, and fine-tuned a BERT-based model to neutralize bias validated with BLEU scores for conformity to original text. They also propose extending typology of Recasens, et al. (2013) into framing, epistemological and demographic bias dimensions, however these are mutually exclusive in their attribution to sentence bias and only a subset of 500 sentences is hand-labelled with this classification, suggesting obvious scalability constraints of hand-labelling. Spinde, et al. (2021) introduce BABE data set for 3700 sentences with bias labels at both word and sentence level based on expert human annotation, and fine-tuned BERT-based models for detection only that outperform prior methods.

While these methods required task-specific fine-tuning, the advent of generative LLMs enabled zero-shot learning (ZSL) for bias reduction. Plaza-del Arco, et al. (2023) propose ZSL approach on

BERT-based encoder and instruction-tuned T5-family of models to achieve competitive or superior performance on some datasets compared to fine-tuned models, though their focus was detecting hate speech, using F1 classification measures based on pre-existing datasets, while noting occasional loss of context. Schlit, et al. (2024) apply ZSL to general-purpose LLMs (OpenAI GPT and Llama variants) in addition to a fine-tuned version of T5-based instruction tuned LLM to debias news text. They also note important, auxiliary impacts of debiasing to factuality, context, grammar and authorship coherence and introduce a multidimensional editorial checklist to assess overall journalistic quality. However, while they note a qualitative variation in “overt bias” and “latent bias”, their editorial checklist includes bias only as a singular scalar score.

These studies underscore the potential of LLMs as accessible debiasing tools while highlighting persistent risks in preserving factual and stylistic integrity. Human evaluation remains the gold standard, though automated metrics (e.g., Perspective API) are used for scalability. However, as Lin et al. (2024) note, LLM-based evaluators being untruthful and misaligned with human judgment from inheriting societal biases is proportional to model size, complicating reliable automated assessment.

Evaluating debiased text remains challenging due to the subjective nature of bias. Existing studies often treat bias monolithically, only identify bias, use fine-tuned models, depend on Perspective API for bias evaluation in unlabelled data despite noting potential unsuitability for news domain, and seldom measure the impact of debiasing on a critical journalistic metric: reader engagement. Our work addresses these gaps by introducing a multi-dimensional concurrent bias-scoring framework (F.E.D. scores), an end-to-end ZSL pipeline for identifying bias in text, rewriting to debias it and evaluating bias afterwards, and underscores additional trade-off between bias reduction and reader engagement. This integrated approach provides a more practical and nuanced understanding of LLMs’ potential and limitations as scalable journalistic aids.

3. Methodology

To address these gaps, we conduct a multi-faceted evaluation of ChatGPT’s ability to function as a debiasing assistant for news sentences. Our study is guided by three research questions:

1. Bias Identification: How proficient is ChatGPT at identifying and explaining specific bias types (emotional, framing, divisive) in news sentences?
2. Bias Reduction: To what extent can ChatGPT rewrite sentences to reduce measured bias?
3. Human Perception: How do human evaluators perceive the bias and engagement quality of ChatGPT-generated rewrites compared to original text?

Pursuant to above questions and based on the literature review concerning LLM behavior we aim to design our methodology for the following, testable outcomes.

O1 (Bias Identification Proficiency)

We evaluate ChatGPT’s bias identification by comparing its ratings for Emotional, Framing, and Divisive language against external benchmarks (e.g., Ad Fontes Media) and by assessing inter-model agreement with other state-of-the-art LLMs.

O2 (Quantitative Bias Reduction and Empirical Failure Patterns)

We measure changes in bias scores for Emotional, Framing, and Divisive language between original and rewritten sentences to quantify bias reduction. Additionally, we will qualitatively identify and categorize common failure patterns in the rewriting process, including:

- Factual Dilution: Replacing specific quantities or claims with vague language.
- Context Stripping: Removing necessary context that, while potentially biased in its original framing, is essential for understanding.
- Over-correction: Neutralizing language that was not inherently biased, leading to stilted or unnatural prose.
- Hallucination: Introducing factual claims not present in the original text.

O3 (Human Perception and Engagement)

We will measure participant preferences for original versus rewritten sentences along two dimensions—perceived bias and engagement—and test for a significant engagement penalty associated with debiased text.

In order to explore these outcomes, we follow a methodology that also makes following four novel contributions:

A Stratified Benchmark

We introduce a carefully curated, stratified primary dataset of 126 biased news sentences to represent a wide spectrum of media bias for controlled analysis.

News sources were selected based on their reliability and bias scores from Ad Fontes Media's Media Bias Chart® (Appendix A), which employs a team of trained human analysts to evaluate content across multiple dimensions. The Ad Fontes bias score scale was stratified into 11 intervals of 6 points each, from -30 to +30. One prominent news website was selected to represent each bias interval, ensuring proportional representation across the political spectrum (Appendix D).

For each selected source, one recent political article was randomly selected. From each selected article, approximately eleven (11) sentences were manually extracted based on two criteria: 1) exhibiting discernible bias (framing, emotional language), and 2) requiring minimal context for standalone evaluation.

The final primary dataset consists of 126 sentences (11 sources * ~11 sentences). Each data point includes the original sentence and its source metadata (URL, source name, Ad Fontes reliability and bias scores).

While modest in size, the curated sampling methodology employed for creating the dataset provides a dependable and reproducible benchmark for evaluating LLM-assisted bias reduction and related future research in this domain (Appendix A).

A 3-dimensional Bias Score

We propose decomposing, interpreting and measuring bias into specific bias characteristics across Framing, Emotional and Divisive dimensions to enable more fine-grained analysis that can be applied

independently of the pipeline discussed in the next section. These dimensions were defined as follows:

Emotionally Charged Language: The use of negative emotions to provoke a reader's opinions in a way that counters objective reality.

Framing Bias: Influencing opinions based on how information is presented rather than on objective facts.

Divisive Language: The use of divisive, tribalistic framing that discourages empathy.

A 3-phase Prompting Pipeline

The sentences from the primary dataset were processed using the OpenAI API to interact with chosen ChatGPT model (OpenAI GPT-3.5-turbo, accessed via API, Oct 2025) through a structured, three-phase (Identify - Rewrite - Evaluate) pipeline that integrates the end-to-end workflow of bias detection, rewriting, and evaluation in a single, structured methodology (Appendix A).

Identify Phase: Each sentence from the primary dataset was submitted to the model with a structured prompt designed to elicit a multi-faceted evaluation of bias. The prompt instructed the model to rate the statement on a scale from 1 to 10 across above 3 dimensions and to provide a qualitative explanation for each rating. The model's response, including its three numerical ratings and qualitative explanations for each criterion, was recorded for every sentence.

Rewrite Phase: In a new, separate chat instance, the model was provided with its own biased explanation from Identify Phase and instructed to rewrite the original sentence. The rewriting directive specified that the output must be more neutral and objective while preserving the core factual information of the original. Crucially, the instruction mandated that the rewrite must specifically address the biased elements the model itself (but in a different instance) had identified in the Identify Phase explanation. The rewritten sentence generated by the model was recorded and paired with the original for subsequent evaluation. A manual empirical analysis would be undertaken to validate the extent to which the prompt directives retained factual information in the rewrite.

Evaluate Phase: Each rewritten sentence was then fed into a new, third chat instance and evaluated for

the F.E.D scores using the same prompt from Identify Phase. This provided a quantitative and qualitative measure of the perceived bias reduction according to the LLM's own criteria.

The effectiveness of ChatGPT's rewriting was validated through two parallel methods:

1. comparing a model's scores to an established external benchmark of Ad Fontes Media Bias Ratings, and
2. assessing consistency between different LLMs scoring the same text. The numerical ratings (1-10) for each bias criterion from Identify Phase (original sentence) and Evaluate Phase (rewritten sentence) were compared. A statistically significant decrease in these scores were used as a metric for the model success in bias reduction.

Larger Corpus Dataset

Building on the validated performance of our prompts in the controlled primary dataset (126 sentences), we applied the same prompting pipeline to generate a larger corpus of 100,000 ChatGPT-rewritten sentences (Appendix B), with each data point comprising of the original sentence, its 3 bias scores along with explanations, the corresponding rewritten sentence and its 3 bias scores of the rewritten sentence.

A web scraper was engineered for high-volume data collection, capable of processing thousands of articles. It fetched new articles from over 80 RSS feeds from major national and international news organizations (e.g., CNN, BBC, Reuters, Fox News, The New York Times) across multiple categories (Politics, Business, Technology, World).

The scraper systematically extracted the full text of linked articles and decomposed them into individual sentences using a combination of the Trafilatura library and custom parsers, followed fair use guidelines for academic research, avoided paywalled content, and respected server load limitations.

This expanded dataset preserves the structure and multi-dimensional bias annotations of the primary data, providing a resource for further research on bias detection, automated debiasing, and evaluation of large-scale generative pipelines, and has been

released under an open-source license to facilitate reproducibility and community use.

Human Perception

To ground the evaluation in human perception, an additional controlled survey was administered as described below.

Fifteen sentences were randomly selected from the primary dataset using a randomized selection process to ensure an unbiased sample. For each of these sentences, participants were presented with a pair of statements consisting of the original sentence and its ChatGPT-generated rewrite. The order of presentation (original/rewrite) was randomized for each pair to avoid sequence bias.

Task: For each pair, participants answered two questions using a continuous slider interface:

- Bias Perception: "Which statement is more biased?"
- Engagement Preference: "Which statement would you be more likely to continue reading and engage with?"

Participants: A sample of 14 participants was recruited. This sample size is consistent with similar qualitative human evaluations in NLP research (Bordia, 2023).

Human evaluation was conducted via a voluntary, minimal-risk survey. Participants were informed of the study purpose, and starting the survey implied consent. No identifying information was collected, and all responses were anonymized. Formal institutional ethics review was not sought due to the minimal-risk nature of the study.

Platform: The survey was deployed via Google Forms to streamline data collection directly from the dataset (Appendix C).

4. Results and Discussion

4.1 Validation of ChatGPT's Bias Detection Capability

Both following analyses, using Spearman's correlation, ρ based on its suitability for ordinal data and monotonic relationships, evaluate ChatGPT's bias detection capability:

Analysis 1: External Validity (ChatGPT vs. Ad Fontes)

For each of the 126 sentences, we calculated the correlation between two ranked lists:

- the average bias score (the average of its three F.E.D. dimension scores)
- the absolute value of the Ad Fontes bias score for each corresponding source

ChatGPT showed statistically significant positive correlations with the external Ad Fontes rankings as it has a score correlation of $\rho=0.548$ with a p-value of 0.04. The significant correlation with Ad Fontes confirms that ChatGPT's bias detection is not arbitrary; it captures trends that align with established, human-annotated media bias classifications, confirming external validity for using ChatGPT as a bias sensor.

Analysis 2: Inter-model Agreement

To assess consistency between the models themselves, we calculated pairwise Spearman correlations. For each of the three bias dimensions (Emotional, Framing, Divisive), we correlated each raw score from ChatGPT against corresponding score from another model (e.g., all Emotional scores from ChatGPT vs. all Emotional scores from Gemini).

Table 1: Inter-Model Agreement: Pairwise Correlation of LLM F.E.D. Scores

Bias Dimension	ChatGPT vs. Gemini	ChatGPT vs. Claude
Emotional	0.559 (p ~1.05e-11)	0.548 (p ~3.19e-11)
Framing	0.553 (p ~1.85e-11)	0.529 (p ~1.94e-10)
Divisive	0.601 (p ~4.67e-14)	0.633 (p ~1.94e-15)

The strong, significant correlations between the LLMs across all dimensions demonstrate high inter-model agreement. This indicates that different state-of-the-art models, when given the same framework (F.E.D.), arrive at highly consistent judgments about the presence and degree of bias in text.

4.2 ChatGPT-Debiasing Rewrite Effectiveness

Significant Bias Reduction in High-Bias Sentences

Analysis of sentences with high initial bias (F.E.D. score ≥ 6) reveals strong performance in bias reduction. As shown in Table 1, the model achieved substantial decreases in its own perceived bias metrics across all three dimensions.

Table 2: Bias Reduction in High-Bias Sentences (Original Score ≥ 6) (Charts in Appendix E)

Bias Type	Original (Avg)	Rewrite (Avg)	Mean Debias	% Debias
Emotional	7.4	1.6	5.8	78.38
Framing	7.8	2.4	5.4	69.23
Divisive	7.2	1.6	5.6	77.78

This analysis reveals a powerful effect: for overtly biased sentences, ChatGPT achieved approximately 70-80% reduction in its own perceived bias metrics. This confirms the model's technical proficiency at identifying and neutralizing highly charged language, manipulative framing, and divisive language.

Qualitative Analysis of Rewriting Trade-offs

A manual review of the original and rewritten sentence pairs reveals the specific linguistic strategies employed by ChatGPT and the associated trade-offs, as a way to validate to what extent the prompt directives for factual retention were successfully adhered.

Successful Strategies: Included neutralizing loaded verbs (e.g., "rammed through a contract" became "approved a contract") and de-escalating divisiveness (e.g., "This sham vote... this sellout" became "Some teachers argue the vote should not be considered valid").

Prevalent Failure Modes: The most significant was Factual Dilution and Context Stripping, exhibited by about a third of the sentences. However, of those, an overwhelming majority were not impacted to a level that would hinder the reader from reaching an informed understanding of its key point. In an

example of larger impact, the original sentence detailing a raise that "does not keep pace with inflation in Philadelphia, which is already higher" was rewritten to the bare fact "The agreement includes a 3 percent annual wage increase...", omitting the comparative economic context.

4.3 Human Evaluation: The Paradox of Bias and Engagement

Bias Perception: Human Validation of ChatGPT's Success

In addition to evaluation of bias perception in Section 4.1, we also examined this finding against the innate sensitivity of human judgment for a convergent validation that the rewriting succeeded in bias reduction in a perceptible, real-world sense. Table 3 captures our findings.

Table 3: Frequency Distribution of Human Bias Ratings

Meaning	Count	Percent
1.Original has much more bias	120	19.08
2.Original has slightly more bias	236	37.52
3.No perceived difference	183	29.09
4.Rewrite has slightly more bias	77	12.24
5.Rewrite has much more bias	13	2.07
Total	629	100

The data shows the combined count for ratings 1 and 2 (Original is more biased) is 356, which is nearly four times greater than the combined count for ratings 4 and 5 (Rewrite is more biased) at 90. This reasonably confirms from a human perspective that the debiasing objective was successfully achieved.

Engagement Penalty: A Preference for Original Content

Despite recognizing the original passages as more biased, participants showed a strong and clear preference for them in terms of engagement per our findings in Table 4.

Table 4: Frequency Distribution of Engagement Choices

Engagement Choice	Count	Percentage
Original	90	43.06%
Rewrite	48	23.00%
Both	32	15.31%
Neither	39	19.00%
Total	209	100%

The original text was selected nearly twice as often as the ChatGPT rewrite. This engagement penalty for debiased text is the most significant finding of human evaluation. It suggests that the stylistic elements the ChatGPT removes to achieve neutrality may be the same elements that make content compelling and engaging to readers. This demonstrates the critical limitation of relying solely on bias detection scores without considering their impact on reader engagement.

5. Conclusion and Future Work

5.1 Summary of Findings

Our analysis, synthesizing all data, yields three key findings:

O1 (Bias Identification Proficiency): From results of external benchmark validation and inter-model agreement Spearman scores ($0.529 \leq \rho \leq 0.633$), we conclude that the ChatGPT model demonstrated high proficiency in identifying bias across all 3 distinct dimensions of bias.

O2 (Quantitative Bias Reduction): a significant (70-80%) reduction was seen in ChatGPT-evaluated scores for high-bias sentences ($FED \geq 6$). Further, an manual empirical analysis against O2 (Empirical Failure Patterns) confirmed reasonable and acceptable adherence to prompt directives in preserving factual content during such debiasing.

O3 (Human Perception and Engagement): Humans confirmed the rewrites were less biased (by a ~4:1 ratio), but preferred the original texts for engagement (by a ~2:1 ratio).

5.2 Limitations and Future Work

While the findings suggest statistically significant findings even with modest dataset sizes and sentence-level analysis, validation with larger

corpuses and context windows would improve exhaustiveness of findings reliability.

Also, a measurement driven validation in place of manual empirical confirmation of factual retention would strengthen the reliability in ChatGPT's abilities.

Future research should focus on bridging the identified gaps:

- Quantitative studies that measure factual and context retention across the 4 error categories identified in Section 3-O2.
- Developing LLM prompts and training strategies that explicitly optimize for the triple balance of low bias, high factual/contextual integrity, and reader engagement.
- Large-scale studies to see if the engagement penalty holds across diverse reader demographics, a wider range of news topics and longer contexts.

5.3 Implications for Practical Application

From our findings, the central challenge is not merely improving bias detection, but systems that can navigate its trade-off against factual and contextual retention, and human engagement. For newsrooms, and readers alike, this trade-off is critical. An autonomous tool that neutralizes language at the expense of engagement and context could produce content that is objectively less biased but subjectively less appealing, potentially reducing the reach and impact of the news.

In conclusion, while ChatGPT demonstrates promising proficiency as a bias detection and neutralization engine, the role of journalism is not merely to be neutral, but to be accurate, contextual, and engaging. Therefore, ongoing research in capabilities and alignment of these tools to journalistic standards remain a promising frontier of exploration.

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